

CLINICAL CHARACTERISTICS AND LABORATORY FINDINGS OF ISCHEMIC HEART DISEASE IN THE PRESENCE OF MULTIPLE COMORBIDITIES

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ABSTRACT

Cardiovascular diseases (CVD) remain the leading causes of global mortality, annually claiming the lives of more than 18 million people [1,2]. Arterial hypertension (AH) and ischemic heart disease (IHD) are the main determinants of critical vascular complications. According to global statistics [3], AH affects more than 1.2 billion people, while IHD is diagnosed in over 120 million. The coexistence of these pathologies is especially common in individuals over 60 years of age, reaching up to 50%, which is linked to excess body weight, lipid metabolism disorders, and chronic inflammation [4,5].

Introduction: Cardiovascular diseases (CVD) remain the leading causes of global mortality, annually claiming the lives of more than 18 million people [1,2]. Arterial hypertension (AH) and ischemic heart disease (IHD) are the main determinants of critical vascular complications. According to global statistics [3], AH affects more than 1.2 billion people, while IHD is diagnosed in over 120 million. The coexistence of these pathologies is especially common in individuals over 60 years of age, reaching up to 50%, which is linked to excess body weight, lipid metabolism disorders, and chronic inflammation [4,5].

Despite advances in pharmacotherapy and preventive strategies, effective control of hypertension is still not achieved in 35–40% of patients, leaving blood pressure levels above the target range and significantly increasing the risk of coronary events and cerebrovascular complications [6,7]. Uncontrolled hypertension is associated with a progressive rise in cardiovascular mortality, reaching 15–20% per decade [8].

The transition from isolated hypertension to its combination with ischemic heart disease is driven by complex mechanisms, including vascular remodeling, impaired microcirculation, systemic inflammation, and metabolic dysregulation. However, the exact pathways of this progression remain insufficiently studied [9].

In this context, it is essential to investigate the role of demographic, regional, and anthropometric factors in the development and course of AH and IHD. Such data may form the basis for more accurate prediction models and targeted prevention, highlighting the importance of this research.

Purpose of the study. The aim of this study was to investigate the gender and regional characteristics of arterial hypertension (AH) and coronary heart disease (CHD), with particular emphasis on their clinical manifestations, anthropometric features, and distribution among different patient categories..

Materials and methods. A comprehensive clinical and laboratory examination was carried out among 120 patients treated at the Bukhara Regional Cardiology Dispensary. All study participants were selected according to predefined inclusion and exclusion criteria to ensure the reliability of the obtained results and minimize the influence of unrelated pathologies.

Patients were divided into three main clinical groups:

Group I (n=40): Patients with isolated ischemic heart disease, without clinically verified comorbid conditions.

Group II (n=40): Patients with ischemic heart disease combined with type 2 diabetes mellitus.

Group III (n=40): Patients with ischemic heart disease combined with chronic kidney disease.

The distribution of patients by age, gender, body mass index, clinical symptoms, hemodynamic parameters, coagulation profile, biochemical blood markers, and general urinalysis was analyzed in detail. Special attention was given to identifying differences between groups in order to assess the impact of comorbid conditions on the course and prognosis of IHD.

Conclusions:

In the analysis of gender distribution, women were more frequent among patients with isolated hypertension, accounting for 61.7% of cases, while in the group with a combination of hypertension and coronary heart disease men predominated (51.7%). Although women dominated in group I (37 out of 60) and men in group II (31 out of 60), these differences did not reach statistical significance ($p=0.144$).

When assessing the place of residence, rural patients predominated in both groups, but their proportion was higher in isolated hypertension (80.0%) compared to the combined pathology (71.7%). The share of urban residents was slightly higher in group II (28.3% versus 20.0%), though this difference was also not statistically significant ($p=0.292$).

The analysis of body mass index revealed more pronounced differences. Excess body weight was more common in patients with isolated hypertension (50.0%) than in those with hypertension and coronary heart disease (40.0%). At the same time, the proportion of patients with normal BMI was significantly higher in group II (30.0% versus 10.0% in group I), which indicates a reliable difference in the distribution of BMI between the groups ($p=0.049$).

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